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Review Article

**ASSESSMENT OF QUALITY OF LIFE IN BREAST CANCER
PATIENTS: A RETROSPECTIVE COHORT STUDY****Kammela Naga Mounika*¹, Mallipeddi Bhargavi¹, Vanukuri Harika¹, Satish Kumar
A², R. Naga Lekhini³, Ramarao Nadendla⁴**^{1,3,4}Chalapathi Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Lam, Guntur²Government General Hospital, Department of Radiotherapy, Guntur**Article Received:** February 2020 **Accepted:** March 2020 **Published:** April 2020**Abstract:**

In India the Breast cancer is the most common type of cancer in women. The patients with breast cancer were facing many problems neither by the disease nor by the treatment side effects. So that measuring quality of life in patients with breast cancer is important for assessing the treatment outcomes. Thus in our study we analysed the impact of treatment on quality of life of women with breast cancer. The purpose of present study is to assess the quality of life in breast cancer patients to manage their treatment and to prevent further progression of disease.

Key words: *Quality of life, Breast cancer, pain, EORTC QLQ BR 45, FACT B.*

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INTRODUCTION:

The uncontrolled and proliferative growth of cells in the breast tissue is known as Breast cancer. It generally occurs in females and it rarely occurs in males. There are different kinds of breast cancer and that differs in the part of it occurs in the breast. Mainly there are three parts in the breast. They are Lobules, Ducts and Connective tissue. Breast cancer is the second most common type of cancer among females in India whereas it is the first most common type of cancer among females in worldwide. In situ breast cancers are non invasive breast cancer. In these types certain aberrations in the cell cause the atypical cells to proliferate and they haven't spread or metastasized beyond the lobules or ducts of the breast. It includes Lobular carcinoma in situ (LCIS) or ductal carcinoma in situ (DCIS). Invasive breast cancers are those tumours which have metastasized from the lobules or ducts of the breast and have started to infiltrate into the normal tissues. The mortality rate was 12.7 per 1 lakh women. Breast cancer was affected in 18 percent of the Indian female population. The most common histological type of breast cancer was the infiltrating duct carcinoma. In Hindu women, the breast cancer was affected in 13 percent of the population. Among Indian females the breast cancer has ranked number one with the age adjusted rate as high as 25.8 per 100,000 women. The mortality rate was 12.7 per 100,000 women.

RESULTS:**Table 1: Age Vs No. of Subjects**

The below table represents the information regarding distribution of subjects within the age groups 21-80.

Age of the subjects	No. of subjects (N= 250)
25-35	18 (7.20%)
36-45	72 (28.80%)
46-55	76 (30.40%)
56-65	62 (24.80%)
66-80	22 (8.80%)

Table 2: Family history Vs Number of Subjects

Our study found that there is an association of family history in development of breast cancer as shown in table 6.

Family history	Number of subjects in %
Yes	142 (56.80%)
No	108 (43.20%)

Table 3: Menstrual irregularities Vs number of subjects

Our study found there is no significant association of menstrual irregularities in development of breast cancer.

Menstrual irregularities	Number of subjects in %
Yes	31.20%
No	68.80%

AIM:

To assess the Quality of Life in patients with Breast Cancer.

OBJECTIVES:

To study and understand the Quality of life in patients with breast cancer by EORTC QLQ BR45 and self designed validated questionnaire.

METHODOLOGY:

A retrospective cohort study was carried out in department of radiotherapy, Government General Hospital, Guntur for duration of 6 months (October 2019 – March 2020) after obtaining approval from institutional ethical committee. A patient who were suffering with breast cancer were included in this study based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria and also taken the inform consent form. The quality of life of breast cancer patients during treatment and after treatment was analysed by using self designed validated questioner (which was taken from EORTC QLQ BR 45 and FACT B) which represents the past and present health status of patients. The patient's data was collected into the data collection form. The obtained data was entered into the advanced Microsoft excel sheet and evaluated. For statistical analysis, Graph pad 8.1.0 was used and paired t- test was done with the 95% confidence interval at alpha 0.05 and p- value was < 0.05 should be considered as significant.

Table 4: Symptoms Vs Number of subjects

The below table provides the information regarding the symptoms experienced by the subjects during and after treatment in breast cancer.

Symptoms (N= 250)	During the treatment		After the treatment	
	Yes	No	Yes	No
Nausea / vomiting	179 (71.60%)	71 (28.40%)	47 (18.80%)	203(81.20%)
Tingling	93 (37.20%)	157 (62.80%)	135 (54%)	115 (46%)
Fatigue	161 (64.40%)	89 (35.60%)	58 (23.20%)	192(76.80%)
Weight loss	145 (58%)	105 (42%)	179 (71.60%)	71 (28.40%)
Cough	200 (80%)	50 (20%)	16 (6.40%)	234(93.60%)
Hair loss	217 (86.80%)	33 (13.20%)	4 (1.60%)	246 (98.4%)
Trouble swallowing	203 (81.20%)	47 (18.80%)	24 (9.60%)	22690.40%)
Sleep disturbances	217 (86.80%)	33 (13.20%)	29 (11.60%)	221(88.40%)
Numbness	89 (35.60%)	161 (64.40%)	148 (59.20%)	102(40.80%)
Skin problems in area of affected breast	147 (58.80%)	103 (41.20%)	93 (37.20%)	157(62.80%)

TABLE 5: FUNCTIONAL STATUS VS NUMBER OF SUBJECTS

The below table provides the information regarding the different functional status during and after the treatment.

Functional status (N=250)	During the treatment		After the treatment	
	Yes	No	Yes	No
Physical functioning	189 (75.60%)	61 (24.4%)	45 (18%)	205 (82%)
Social function	114 (45.60%)	136 (54.40%)	105 (42%)	145 (58%)
Emotional functioning	132 (52.80%)	118 (47.20%)	68(27.20%)	182(72.80%)

TABLE 6: PAINFUL SITES VS NUMBER OF SUBJECTS

The below table depicts that the subjects experienced the pain in different sites during the treatment and after the treatment.

Painful site (N=250)	During treatment		After treatment	
	Yes	No	Yes	No
Breast area	145	105	168	82
Stomach	2	248	0	250
Hip	5	245	9	241
Legs	146	104	189	61
Arms / shoulders	135	115	164	86

TABLE 7: PAIN INTERFERENCE Vs NUMBER OF SUBJECTS

The below table shows that most of the patients having a pain during bending/climbing and while strenuous activity at after the treatment.

PAIN INTERFERENCE (N=250)	During the treatment		After the treatment	
	Yes	No	Yes	No
Pain while walking	53.85%	46.15%	58.95%	41.05%
Pain while sitting	43.75%	56.25%	23.08%	76.92%
Pain when trying to stand up	34.61%	65.39%	19.23%	80.77%
Pain while lying down	21.15%	78.85%	5.77%	94.23%
Pain inferring sleep	73.08%	26.92%	36.54%	63.46%
Pain while climbing the stairs/ bending	26.92%	73.08%	63.46%	36.54%
Pain with strenuous activity	34.61%	65.39%	44.85%	55.15%

DISCUSSION:

A non-experimental retrospective observational study was carried out on "ASSESSMENT OF QUALITY OF LIFE IN PATIENTS WITH BREAST CANCER" 250 patients met the inclusion criteria and were included in the study. The data obtained was tabulated and analysed. For the assessment of results we categorised the obtained patients within the age of 25-80 years were as follows. In our study we found that majority of the patients were under the age group of 46-55 years (30.40%) followed by 36-45 years (28.80%), 56-65 years (24.80%), 66-80 years (8.80%) and 25-35 years (7.20%). For the assessment of health-related quality of life, we used the EORTC QLQ BR 45 and self designed questionnaire which consists of 45 questions. In our study we calculated the different symptoms. The following information was obtained regarding the symptoms experienced by the subjects during the treatment and those symptoms was nausea/vomiting (71.60%), tingling (37.20%), fatigue (64.40%), weight loss (58%), cough (80%), hair loss (86.80%), trouble swallowing (81.20%), sleep disturbances (86.80%), numbness (35.60%) and skin problems in area of affected breast (58.80%). After the treatment the experienced symptoms and percentage was nausea/vomiting (18.80%), tingling (54%), fatigue (23.20%), weight loss (71.60%), cough (6.40%), hair loss (98.40%), trouble swallowing (9.60%), sleep disturbances (11.60%), numbness (59.20%) and skin problems in area of affected breast (37.20%). The health-related quality of life was different for the different symptoms. A p value (0.022*) was considered to be significant. Based on the individual symptoms like nausea/ vomiting the health quality of life was improved and for the tingling and numbness the health-related quality of life was reduced because of the chemotherapy side effect. The other symptoms like hair loss, trouble swallowing, sleep disturbances, skin problems in area of effected breast the health-related quality of life was improved. In our study we assessed the results based on the different functional status like physical functioning consists of 2 items (33, 40 questions), social functioning consists of 4 items (8, 9, 10, 11 questions) and emotional functioning consists of 1 item (17 question). The results obtained for the physical functioning (75.6%), social function (45.60%) and emotional functions (52.80%) in during the treatment and also the physical functioning (18%), social function (42%) and emotional functions (27.20%) after the treatment. A p value (0.02*) was considered to be significant. By the obtained results the functional related quality of life has improved. In our study we assessed the pain related quality of life. We used the questioner it depicts that the most of the subjects experienced the pain during the treatment

as well as after the treatment. The painful sites were breast area, stomach, hip, legs and arm/shoulder. In our study we assessed the pain interference in during the treatment and after the treatment. The pain interference was pain while walking, sitting, trying to stand up, lying down, sleep, climbing the stairs or bending and strenuous activity. During the treatment pain while walking (53.85%), pain while sitting (43.75%), pain when trying to stand up (34.61%), pain while lying down (73.08%), pain while climbing the stairs or bending (26.92%) and pain with strenuous activities (34.61%). After the treatment the results were pain while walking (58.95%), pain while sitting (23.08%), pain when trying to stand up (19.23%), pain while lying down (5.77%), pain interfering sleep (36.54%), and pain while climbing the stairs or bending (63.46%) and pain with strenuous activity (44.85%). The most of the patients experiencing pain during bending/climbing followed by pain interfering sleep, pain while walking, pain while sitting, pain with strenuous activity, pain when trying to stand up, pain while lying down during the treatment. After the treatment the pain interfering sleep, pain while walking, pain while sitting, and pain with strenuous activity, pain when trying to stand up, pain while lying down. Overall the pain interference related quality of life in breast cancer patient was reduced. In our study we also found that an association of family history for the development of breast cancer.

CONCLUSION:

Based on the results obtain our study concluded that overall quality of life of breast cancer patients was improved after adjuvant treatment. But pain related quality of life has not improved in breast cancer patients after treatment.

LIMITATION:

This study included only 250 patients for the "ASSESSMENT OF QUALITY OF LIFE IN BREAST CANCER PATIENTS: A RETROSPECTIVE OBSERVATIONAL STUDY" 20 members were excluded because they were not willing to give information. This study can be extended by taking a more number of follow ups.

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